

2015-2016 ANNUAL REPORT
 COMMISSION B5 LABORATORY ASTROPHYSICS
http://www.iau.org/science/scientific_bodies/commissions/B5/

IAU Commission B5 activities 2015/2016

- The Laboratory Astrophysics Commission (Commission B5) came into being at the IAU 29th GA in Hawaii in 2015
- The elected organizing committee (OC) is composed of: Farid Salama (Founding President), Helen Fraser (Vice President), Gianfranco Vidali (Secretary), Paul Barklem, Thomas Henning, Harold Linnartz, Feilu Wang
- Commission B5 has 137 members
- The various activities and discussions for the most part take place through email consultation among the OC.
- The Commission communicates with its members through the IAU mass mailing system (e.g., to inform the members of the Commission about meetings and conferences of interest, announcements of interest such as International research agreements and job opportunities)
- The first Working Group (WG) of the Commission, WG on High-Accuracy Stellar Spectroscopy, was initiated by Paul Barklem and launched in February 2016.
- The WG on High-Accuracy Stellar Spectroscopy promotes high-accuracy atomic and molecular data required for accurate stellar spectroscopy and is chaired by Paul Barklem with four supporting members from Commission B5 (Sultana Nahar, Juliet Pickering, Norbert Przybilla, Tatiana Ryabchikova).
- Commission B5 has endorsed a proposal for a Symposium at IAU 2018 and a proposal for a Focus Meeting at IAU 2018.
- The OC of Commission B5 has submitted a proposal to organize and hold the first IAU Laboratory Astrophysics Symposium as a non-GA IAU Symposium in 2018.
- The proposed Symposium is entitled: "Laboratory Astrophysics: from Observations to Interpretation". The SOC of the proposed Symposium is composed of Paul Barklem (CB5 OC), Helen Fraser (CB5 OC), Thomas Henning (CB5 OC), Sun Kwok (CF3), Harold Linnartz (CB5 OC), Tom Millar (CH2), Farid Salama, Chair (CB5 OC), Gianfranco Vidali (CB5 OC), Feilu Wang (CB5 OC), Giulio Del-Zanna (DE).
- Commission B5 seeks connections with other IAU Divisions and Commissions.
- The President of CB5 (Salama) is a member of the SOC of IAU S332, Astrochemistry VII – Through the Cosmos from Galaxies to Planets, organized by the Astrochemistry Commission (CH2) to be held in Chili in March 2017.
- The President of the Astrochemistry Commission CH2 (Millar) and the President of the Astrobiology Commission CF3 (Kwok) are members of the SOC of the non-GA IAU Symposium "Laboratory Astrophysics: from Observations to Interpretation" proposed by CB5 for 2018.
- The President of CB5 (Salama) is a member of the SOC for the proposed Focus Meeting "Nano Dust in Space and Astrophysics" for IAU 2018 GA by Commission E3, Solar Impact Throughout the Heliosphere.